

THE ROLE OF PLANETS IN LEADING TO UNMARRIED STATUS

J. Venkatraman*, Dr. N. G. Kumaran** & Dr. K. Jothimani***

* Research Scholar, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

*** Associate Professor & HOD of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies (VISTAS), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: J. Venkatraman, Dr. N. G. Kumaran & Dr. K. Jothimani, “The Role of Planets in Leading to Unmarried Status”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 7, Issue 2, Page Number 23-32, 2022.

Copy Right: © IJSRME, 2022 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

It is said that in the divine pattern of earthly life, human beings experience the fruits of their karmas of earlier births in their current ones. It is also believed that (Saneeswara Bhagavan) Saturn, has been deputed by God to make sure that individuals undergo the fruits of their karmas, good or bad. The powerful influence of Saturn can be seen in the fact that out of the 12 Rasis in a horoscope, Saturn is in evidence in 6 of them. This is to say, Saturn’s influence can be seen in at least half the events in our lives. Saturn dispenses the good and bad effects of our karma, dispassionately. He takes a slightly less severe stance in the case of those who are in Makara (Capricorn), Kumbha (Aquaris), Rishaba (Taurus) and Tula (Libra) Rasis.

Introduction:

The part played by Saturn in the delay in marriage is extremely important. When the Houses that aid the happening of marriage 2,7 and 11th, have direct connection with the marriage causing planets, Venus, Sun and Moon & 7th Bavathypathy the marriage is not likely to happen or there will be inordinate delay, no matter how much effort is made. On the other hand if the Dasa, Bukthi and Antharam, during the individual’s marriage age, have a connection with 2, 7 and 11th Houses, the marriage takes place. The 12th House from 2, 7 and 11th Houses that is Lagna 6 and 10th Houses will not aid the happening of marriage. However, Lagna is neutral.

Men cannot fight Fate. Despite having good looks, education, wealth and status, if a person is unable to marry during his or her marriageable age and enjoy the comforts of marriage, their lives are wasted. If planetary positions are like those given below, the happening of marriage is difficult.

- If Saturn aspects marriage causing planet, Venus, and also either Sun or Moon, the unaspected planet, Sun or Moon, should be in Saturn Rasi or Navamsha.
- If the 5th Lord and the 7th Lord mutually exchanged, this could lead to marriage never happening. If the influence of an auspicious planet is strong enough, it could lead to a delayed marriage.
- If Rahu is connected to an inauspicious planet in either 7th or 9th House. If Rahu and Venus are united in 7th House of Lagna, this will also cause a hurdle for the marriage.
- If 7th House Lord and 7th House, the Sun, Moon are in fixed Rasis.
- If 9th House or 9th House Lord become inauspicious. In addition to this, if Saturn is connected to the 9th Lord or House by association or aspect, marriage will be delayed.
- If Moon and Venus are united and Saturn and Mars are in 7th House from Moon and Venus, the individual will not be interested in marriage
- If Sun and Saturn are united in Lagna or they are in 2/12 position for 7th Lord, 7th Bhava or Lagna this combination will result in delayed marriage or even not marrying at all.
- If Venus is between Sun and Moon, this position will lead to delayed marriage or even marriage never happening. If Venus is in the same position in Kataka (Cancer) or Simham (Leo), it will definitely lead to a hurdle in marriage taking place.
- If Saturn’s influence is in the 2nd, 7th or 11th Bhavas. Also, if Sun and Moon and Venus are influenced by Saturn or a nonaspected planet is in Saturn’s Rasi or Navamsa the chances of getting married are very few.
- If Saturn is retrograded, the influence of Saturn in delaying the marriage will be very powerful.
- If 7th House Lord, Venus or Jupiter is united with Saturn or if they are in the 7th House from Saturn and if they have no connection with any auspicious planet, marriage will be either delayed or not take place at all.
- If at the time of the marriage age the Dasa, Bukthi, Antharam are related to 2, 7 and 11th Bhavas there may not be any problem. If at that time the Dasa, Bukthi, Antharam of Lagna 6 and 10th Bhavas that is the 12th Bhavas of 2, 7, 11 happen the marriage will not take place. In such a situation, an earlier love affair may also fail. In these conditions Lagna will take a neutral path.

- If the distance between Sun and Venus is more than 43 degrees 20 minutes, the marriage will be delayed to the extent of not taking place.
- If 7th Bavathipathi and Bava, Venus, Jupiter, fall in Paapakathiyoga there will be a delay in marriage.

The exemptions for these condition are:

- If Jupiter and Saturn together in 7th House are as the Lords of 5 and 7th Bavas.
- If Tula (Libra) Rasi happens to be the 7th House and if Jupiter is placed here.
- If Meena (Pisces) Rasi happens to be in the 7th House and if Saturn is placed there.
- If Lagna and the 7th House become strong and have powerful benefic aspects.

The Influence of Dasa, Bukthi, Antharam in Non-Marriage:

Some horoscopes are given as examples of unmarried state in Umang Tanija’s book ‘Astrology & Relationship’.

Female - Star: Tiruvonam - Makaram - Chandra Dasha 09.2.19

Asc/ Mar R Jup Sun	Ven Mer				Asc/ Mar	Moo	Mer Rah	
Rah	Rasi 01.04.51				Sat	Navamsam		Jup
Moo	06.50 Delhi P. 150			Ket M				
			Sat R		Sun M	Ket		Ven

Chandra Dasa : upto yrs. 09 Age – 1960 Jupitef Dasa : upto yrs. 50 Age - 2001
 MarsDasa : upto yrs. 16 Age – 1967 Satturn Dasa : upto yrs. 69 Age - 2020
 Rahu Dasa : upto yrs. 34 Age – 1985

	Asc	27.58	Revathy 4	1.2	Jupiter	02.03	Poorattathi 4
1.3	Sun	17.20	Revathy 1	1.3	Venus	19.42	Barani 2
1.3	Moon	11.02	Tiruvonam 1	1.3	SaturnR	04.55	Uthiram 3
1.2	MarsR	29.56	Revathy 4		Rahu	24.50	Poorattathi 2
1.3	Mercury	05.20	Aswini 2		Ketu	24.50	Pooram 4

Planetary Positions Causing Delay in Marriage:

- Retrograded Saturn is in 7th House.
- Inauspicious planets Mars and Sun are united with Jupiter and are aspecting retrograded Saturn in the 7th House. Thus 7th house has three malefic connections.
- Retrograded Saturn is aspecting all three Planets – Mars, Jupiter & Sun from 7th House.
- Moon is in Saturn’s Makara (Capricorn) Rasi.
- Rahu is in the Lagna Lord’s Star, Jupiter who is neutral. Jupiter is also the 10th Lord. Rahu is in the 12th Bava and in Saturn’s Kumba (Aquaris) Rasi who is neutral as far as marriage.
- Second Bava Lord Mars has not only been combusted by 6th Lord, Sun, he is also in the 4 minute Sandhi (29.56). Also, the second Bava Lord is not encouraging the taking place of the marriage.
- 7th Lord, Mercury, is in Kethu’s Star who is in 6th Bava. These conditions do not allow the growth of the desire to get married.
- 2nd House Lord, Mars has been combusted by 6th Bavathipathi and being associated with Jupiter, Bavathipathi of 1 and 10, and Sun, 6th Bavathipathi, these will not allow the individual to even consider life with a partner. The individual has Rahu Dasa during her marriageable age.
- Rahu, in 12th House and in Jupiter’s star who is neutral as Laganathipathi and prevents as 10th Lord in the matter of marriage. Rahu, in Saturn’s House, who is in 6th Bavathipathi Sun’s star, preventing marriage.
- Let us analyse the dasa, buthi

Jupiter Dasha:

Jupiter is 1-10 Lord and is in his Rasi and star and is therefore strong. 2nd Bavathipathi, Mars, who is in Sandhi with Jupiter is in the star of 7th Bavathipathi, Mercury. 6th Bavathipathi, Sun, combusts 2nd Bavathipathi, Mars. As a result, Jupiter is not in a position to get the marriage done. The retrograded Saturn in 7th Bava aids this.

Saturn Dasha:

11-12 Bavathipathi, Saturn, who is retrograde is in Lagna 7th House, and is both retrograded and in 6th Bavathipathi Sun’s star. He is also aspected by 2nd Bavathipathi, Mars, 6th Bavathipathi, Sun, and 1-10 Bavathipathi, Jupiter. As a result, marriage is a pipe dream for this individual during this Dasha.

Male (Kanchi Maha Periyava) - Sunday - Anusham - Shivayogam - Koula:

Rah Ven		Sun Jup Mer R			Sun		Ket	Jup
Mar	Kanchi Periyava Rasi 20.05.1894 13.18 Villupuram				Mar Mer R	Navamsam		
			Asc/		Ven			
	Moo		ket Sat			Moo Rah	Asc/ M	Sat R

Satturn Dasa03 - 10 – 13

	Asc	22.11	Pooram 3	1.5	Jupiter	17.58	Rohini 3
1.5	Sun	06.53	Karthika 4	1.3	Venus	22.12	Revathy 2
1.3	Moon	14.00	Anusam 4	1.0	Satturn	26.51	Chithra 2
1.2	Mars	14.50	Sadayam 3		Rahu	15.25	Uthirattathi 4
0.9	Mercury R	06.29	Karthika 3		Ketu	15.25	Hastham 2

Planetary Positions Causing Delay in Marriage:

- Retrograted Saturn, along with Kethu, in 2nd Bava, aspects Venus who is in the star of 2-11 Bavathipathi, Mercury. Saturn also aspects Rahu who is in Saturn's star, 11th Bava and Moon who is in his star. These fulfill four conditions out of six for marriage not taking place. If we consider Moon instead of Saturn Rasi is in Saturn's Star. Therefore the chances of getting married are small.
- 4-9 Bavathipathi, Mars is in 7th Bava aspects 7th Bavathipathi Saturn.
- 8th Bavathipathi Jupiter and 10th Bavathipathi, Venus, have exchanged houses.

2-11 Bavathipathi, Mercury, is neutral. He is in Lagnathipathi Sun's star and in union with Jupiter in 10th Bava. As a result, the chances of marriage taking place are low. Also, Mercury is combusted by Sun. In the sage's time, people usually got married very young. Until his 3rd year, there is Saturn Dasa. Then there is Mercury Dasa. Although Mercury, who encourages marriage and is Lord of 2-11 Bavas, he is in Sun's star and is combusted by Sun. As Sun is Lagna Lord, he is neutral. But, as Mercury, sun, along with Jupiter, are in the 10th Bava, they squash any desire to get married. Instead they encourage asceticism.

Kethu Dasa:

Kethu, a planet that does not encourage marriage, is in 2nd Bava, along with 6th Bavathipathi, Saturn, and in the star of 12th Bavathipathi, Moon and as a result, nips in the bud any natural desire to get married.

Venus Dasa:

10th Bavathipathi, Venus and 8th Bavathipathi, Jupiter, are in exchange of houses. Also, Venus is in the star of Mercury who is in 10th Bava and has been combusted by Sun. As a result, marriage cannot take place.

Sun Dasa:

Although Lagna Lord Sun is neutral, as he is in the 10th Bava, he does not aid marriage.

Moon Dasa:

12th Bavathipathi, Moon, is in 4th Bava and in the star of 6th Bavathipathi, Saturn. As a result, there is no possibility of marriage.

As Kanchi Periyava had to take to asceticism at a very young age and had to succeed the previous Guru, there was no possibility of he is getting married. But the matter was researched by studying the position of planets in his horoscope.

Sringeri Acharya - Abhinava Vidyatheertha - Sunday - Hastam - Krishna Patsa Dwadasi - Preeti - Thaithulam:

		JupR	Asc/ Ket			Sun Moo Jup R	Asc/ Mer Rah
	Sringeri Sankaracharya Rasi 11.11.1917 20.20 Bangalore		Sat			77.35 E Navamsam 12.59 N	Ven Mar
			Mar		Sat		
Ven Rah		Sun Mer	Moo		Ket		

Chandra Dasa - 07 - 03 – 16

	Asc	28.01	Punarpoosam3	1.0	JupiterR	16.06	Rohini 2
0.7	Sun	25.27	Visakam 2	1.1	Venus	11.38	Moolam 4
1.4	Moon	13.36	Hastham 2	1.4	Satturn	21.37	Ayilyam 2
1.6	Mars	11.56	Maham 4		Rahu	09.47	Moolam 2
1.2	Mercury	29.49	Visakam 3		Ketu	09.47	Tiruvathirai1

Planetary Positions Causing Delay in Marriage:

Venus is 46 degrees (4.30 + 30.00 + 11.40 = 46.10) ahead of Sun. That alone is enough reason for denial of marriage. 7th Bavathipathi, Jupiter and 5-12Bavathipathi Venus are in exchange of houses. The exchange of 7th and 5th Bavathipathis makes for non-marriage. Although there is exchange as 12th Bava, the Buthi Venus is 5th Bavathipathi also. Saturn, who is in 2nd Bava, aspects Moon in 4th Bava and also 11th Bava. All this causes delay in marriage leading to denial of marriage. 6th Bavathipathi in 3rd Bava causes delayed marriage. In the Acharya's time, early marriage was the norm. But until he was 14, he had Mars Dasa. Venus, Raghu Association in 7th Bhava is also one of the major reason for non marriage. Analysing the Dasa, Buthi:

Mars Dasa:

6-11 Bavathipathi, Mars aspects 6th Bava and his own Rasi. Also, he is in Kethu's star. The planets in the horoscope do not aid marriage.

Rahu Dasa:

Rahu is in 7th Bava along with Venus. This causes delayed marriage. But both planets are in the grip of Kethu. As Venus is far from sun, Venus does not encourage marriage and also keeps Rahu under control. This is aided by Jupiter exchange. It is strange that in the horoscopes of both these famous Madathipathis, there is Jupiter-Venus exchange.

Jupiter Dasa:

Jupiter, Bavathipathi of 7 and 10 Bavas, is in Vakra in 12th Bava both in Rasi & Amsa. As 10th Bavathipathi did not allow any thoughts ever of getting married.

Sri Jayendra Saraswathi, Kanchi Acharya - Thursday - Avittam - Krishna Patsa Thiruthiyai - Ayushman - Vrishti:

			Mer Ket		Sat R	Jup		Ket
Sat R Moo	Jeyendra Saraswathi Rasi		Sun			77.35 E Navamsam 12.59 N		Sun
Asc/	18.07.1935 18.39 Thanjavur		Ven		Asc/ Mer			Ven
Rah		Mar Jup			Rah	Moo	Mar	

Mars dasa - 01 - 02 - 17

	Asc	02.40	Uthiradam 2	1.1	Jupiter	20.32	Visakam 1
1.2	Sun	02.01	Punarpoosam4	1.1	Venus	15.59	Pooram 1
1.1	Moon	04.21	Avittam 4	1.2	Saturn R	21.37	Sadayam 4
1.3	Mars	01.13	Chithra 3		Rahu	02.02	Uthiradam 1
1.3	Mercury	12.01	Tiruvathirai2		Ketu	20.02	Punarpoosam3

Planetary Positions Causing Delay in Marriage:

Retrograded Saturn along with Moon aspects Venus, who is in Sima (Leo) Rasi. In addition he aspects 11th Bava. Venus is in 8th House. These four factors will lead to delayed marriage that could turn into a state of no marriage. Venus in Sima (Leo) Rasi, retrograded Saturn who along with Moon aspects 7th House; in the adjacent Rasi, Sun is in the Kataka (Cancer) Rasi – all this will cause delayed marriage that could lead to no marriage. 7th Bavathipathi along with retrograded Saturn is in 2nd House, united with Saturn in fixed (Sthira) Rasi. This again leads to delayed marriage. In 7th House from Lagna is Sun who is the 8th Lord. In the 10th Bava is 3 – 12 Bavathipathi Jupiteris united with Mars 4 -11 Bavathipathi. These factors too lead to delayed marriage.

Rahu Dasa:

The period lasts until the individual is 19. The age of marriage has not yet arrived.

Jupiter Dasa:

The 3 -12 Bavathipathi, Jupiter, is united with 4 -11 Bavathipathi, Mars, in 10th Bava. These factors lead to delayed marriage.

Saturn Dasa:

There are some chances of marriage during Saturn Dasa but as the Acharya became an ascetic during his Rahu Dasa itself, the issue of marriage did not arise at all.

Ramana Maharishi - Punarvasu - Tuesday - Viruthi - Karasai - Krishna Patsa Diwidiyai:

Sat	Mar		Ket Moo				Ket	Moo
Jup	Ramana Maharishi Rasi 30.12.1879 01.00 Madurai				Jup	77.35 E Navamsam 12.59 N		Ven
					Mer			Sun
Sun Rah	Ven Mer		Asc/		Sat	Rah	Mar	Asc/

Jupiter Dasa - 06 - 00 - 00:

	Asc	28.43	Chithrai 2	1.2	Jupiter	16.29	Sadayam 3
0.9	Sun	15.35	Pooradam 1	1.2	Venus	00.29	Visakam 4
1.5	Moon	28.20	Punarpoosam 3	1.3	Satturn	17.03	Revathy 1
1.5	Mars	21.58	Bharani 3		Rahu	23.21	Pooradam 4
1.0	Mercury	23.06	Kettai 2		Ketu	23.21	Punarpoosam 2

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

Saturn is in 7th Bava – as an exception to the rule of delayed marriage, for Kanni (Virgo) Lagna, if Saturn is in 7th Bava, it will rectify all the effects of planets causing delay in marriage. By this horoscope this individual’s chances of getting married are high. Also, 11th Lord Moon and Mars, who is aspecting 2nd Bava from Moolatrikona Rasi, get higher Satbala strength (1.5) and will try to make the marriage happen. As everyone knows about Ramana Maharishi’s life, we will simply study the planets that encourage asceticism. If we did not know that this was Ramana’s horoscope, it would be difficult to guess that this individual hated the idea of marriage, that he even found his clothes a burden and undertook Sanyas early.

One of the conditions that lead to asceticism is the link between 4, 12 Bavathipathis, Rahu or Kethu. In Ramana’s horoscope, 4th Bavathipathi Jupiter is in Rahu’s star; 12th Bavathipathi Sun is associated with Rahu in 4th Bava 6th Bavathipathi Saturn is in exchange with 7th Bavathipathi Jupiter. Both are fairly strong in Satbala, because of this. Kanni (Virgo) Lagna’s Bhadhakathipathi, Jupiter, is in 7th Bava bhadakam. As a result he stalls marriage. In 6th Bava, Saturn is not in a position to encourage marriage. In Ramana’s times boys often got married at 12. At that age it was Saturn Dasa in Ramana’s horoscope. The planet that causes marriage is Venus and he is 2nd Bavathipathi. He is in 3rd Bava and in Bhadhakathipathi Jupiter’s star and is linked to 10th Bavathipathi Mercury. This results in hatred for marriage.

11th Bavathipathii, Moon, being in 10th Bava with Kethu creates dislike for marriage. According to Kala Purusha theory, 11 and 12 Bavathipathi, i.e, Saturn, Jupiter exchange, causes hatred for marriage. The Influence of Saturn Dasa runs upto 25 years. The Sun, Lord of 12 is in the 4th Bava, aspected by Saturn. This condition can cause a delay in marriage but not push the individual to a no marriage state. There is an exchange of houses between 7th Bavathipathi Jupiter plus 6th Bavathipathi Saturn. This again will not cause no marriage. 6th Bavathipathi Saturn is in 10th Bavathipathi Mercury’s star. This will lead to a state of no marriage in that Dasa, Bukthi.

Moon and Kethu in 10th Bava are in Jupiter’s star who is in 6th Bava. This will lead to no desire for marriage. Instead Kethu and Jupiter’s influence created a desire towards the Divine. This impelled Ramana to walk miles and miles to reach Tiruvannamalai and have Darshan of Arunachaleswara in Saturn Dasa and Bukthi. Moon, 11th Bavathipathi, is in 10th Bava which is 12th Bava from his own Bava. Therefore the normal desires that are encouraged by 11th House are nullified by the 12th position in which the 11th Lord, Moon is in. That is why Ramana did not wish to wear even clothes and was content to wear a loin cloth alone whatever be the weather.

Exchange Yogam:

Planetary positions that overthrow hurdles to marriage. Meena (Pisces) Lagna becoming the 7th Bava and Saturn residing in it. As such planets are not exactly banning marriage. Therefore the timing of marriage has to be decided only on the basis of Dasa, Bukthi and Antharam. Although it is well known that Ramana Maharishi never married, the planets in his horoscope do not exactly forbid marriage. Taking into account the exchange of planets, Jupiter is in 7th Bava and Saturn in 6th Bava. When the Dasa, Bukthi is calculated on this basis, they can be seen to take the individual to a non –marriage state. In Ramana’s times, boys were married as early as 10. At the time of marriage, there is Rahu Dasa. Through exchange Saturn comes to the 6th Bava. As this is his Moolatrikona position, he also gains strength. Further, no planet has a Satbala strength of more than 1.5. As a result they are unable to encourage marriage. That is why Saturn, in 6th Bava has not aided marriage.

Moon and Kethu, in 10th position are in Jupiter’s star. This aids a growing desire to know the divine. As a result Ramanar went to Tiruvannamalai to have Darshan of Arunachaleswara and became an ascetic. 2nd Lord Venus is in 3rd House and in Jupiter’s star. This created hatred in Ramana a hatred for all material

possessions, even clothes. The exchange of houses between Jupiter & Saturn has mollified the advantage he gets in Saturn in Meena for Kanni Lagna. This also created the hatreds in Ramana's mind as per as marriage is concerned.

Rajan - Sunday - Swathi - Viruthi - Bhava - Krishna Patsa Sapthami:

Asc/	Sat Mar	Jup	M		Moo	Ket	M	Ven R Jup
Ket	Rajan Rasi					Navamsam		
Ven R Mer R Sun	08.02.1942 09.12 Wandavasi		Rah					Sun
		Moo			Sat		Asc/ Mar Rah	Mer R

Rahu Dasa - 00 - 11 - 15:

	Asc	10.15	Uthirattathi 3	1.3	Jupiter	18.22	Rohini 3
1.1	Sun	25.43	Avittam 1	1.3	VenusR	16.55	Tiruvonam 3
0.9	Moon	19.18	Swathi 4	0.9	Satturn	28.50	Karthika 1
1.3	Mars	21.22	Bharani 3		Rahu	21.47	Pooradam 3
1.3	Mercury RC	29.38	Avittam 2		Ketu	23.21	Poorattathi 3

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

According to Trivedi's theory, if Saturn has link with 2, 7, 11 Bavas and planets Sun, Moon and Venus are linked, there is likely to be no marriage. At the very least, there will be very delayed marriage. Saturn along with Mars, aspecting Moon with 7th aspect, Sun residing in Saturn's Rasi will cause delayed marriage. The retrograde state of 7th Bavathipathi, Mercury being combusted by Sun and the retrograde state of Venus, the planet causing marriage, are all planetary positions causing delayed marriage.

In this horoscope Saturn is in 2nd Bava and joined to 2nd Bavathipathi. Mercury is combusted by Sun. Venus, Mercury and Sun are aspected by Saturn. Out of six conditions of the rule for non-marriage, five conditions apply. The sixth condition is 7th Bava should be involved. This does not apply in this horoscope. Instead of 7th Bavathipathi, Mercury gets involved, producing the same result - non-marriage. According to Dasa, Bukthi calculations, this individual has Jupiter Dasa until he is 17, Saturn Dasa until he is 36, Mercury Dasa until he is 53 and Kethu Dasa until he is 60.

Jupiter Dasa: He has not reached marriageable age during this Dasa period.

Saturn Dasa: 11, 12 Bavathipathi, Saturn is in Neechabhangam and along with enimical Rasi Lord, Mars. Saturn is in 6th Lord, Sun's star. Saturn is in the 7th Bava from Moon.

Saturn aspects (10th aspect) retrograded Venus and retrograded 7th Bavathipathi, Mercury and Sun. Sun is in Saturn's Rasi. That is why there was no marriage for this individual.

Mercury Dasa: The same reasons given above led to non -marriage.

Kethu Dasa: Kethu is in 12th Bava. He is in the star of 10th Bavathipathi and Lagnathipathi Jupiter, who is neutral. Kethu generally does not encourage marriage.

Venus Dasa: 3 – 8 Bavathipathi, Venus, is retrograded and is in 11th Bava joined to 6th Lord Sun and combusted 7th Lord Mercury. Because of this, Venus is neutral. As the marriage age is already well past, there has been no marriage in this individual's life.

Kripananda Variar - Swathy:

			Jup		Sat R		Sun Ket
Sat R	Kirubananda Variyar Rasi		Asc / Mer Mar Rah		Mar	Ven	
Ket	25.08.1906 04.35 Vellore		Sun		Moo Mer Jup	Navamsam	
		Moo	Ven		Asc/ Rah		

Rahu Dasa -12 - 01 - 14:

	Asc	19.02	Ayilyam 1	1.2	Jupiter	12.12	Tiruvathirai 2
1.3	Sun	08.18	Maham 3	1.4	Venus	22.49	Hastham 4
1.1	Moon	11.01	Swathi 2	1.3	Satturn R	19.56	Sadayam 4

1.5	Mars	25.39	Ayilyam 3		Rahu	19.03	Ayilyam 1
1.3	Mercury RC	21.40	Ayilyam 2		Ketu	19.03	Tiruvonam 3

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

7th Lord Saturn is retrograded and in the 8th Bava. Retrograded Saturn in 8th Bava aspects 2nd Bava and 2nd Bava Lord, Sun, who is in his own house. Moon is in Saturn's Rasi in Navamsa. Eunuch planet Kethu is alone in 7th Bava. 4-11 Bava Lord Venus (who promotes marriage) is in Neecha and in 3rd Bava. As a rule, if Venus between Sun and Moon, it will lead to delayed marriage or no marriage. Mars in Neecha aspects retrograded Saturn. While retrograded 7th Bavathipathi, Saturn's aspect causes delayed marriage, the arrangement of the other planets lead to a state of no marriage.

Dasa Bukthi: In Variar's time child marriage was the norm. As such, we should study the Jupiter Dasa that occurs during Variar's 12th year.

Jupiter Dasa: 6th Lord Jupiter is in Rahu's star, in the 12th Bava. Jupiter is in Neecha in Navamsa. Jupiter gets 7th Bava connection through Rahu, Mars whose Satbala is strong, as Mars is 10th Bavathipathi, there is no chance of the marriage taking place.

Saturn Dasa: Although Saturn is 7th Bavathipathi, as he is retrograded and in 8th Bava and has been connected to Sun and Moon.

As 10th Lord Mars' 8th aspect is towards 7th Bava, there is no help for the marriage to take place.

The most important reasons for the marriage not taking place is the placement of Venus between Sun and Moon and Saturn aspecting Sun and Moon is in Saturn's Rasi in Navamsa. Fortunately Venus escaped Saturn's aspect but he also did not aid the happening of marriage because he is near Adhineecha position.

“Predicting Marriage”- by Trivedi - Sample Horoscope 113 - Female - Bharani - Sukla Patsa Sapthami - Bramham – Karasai:

Ven	Moo Jup	Rah	Mar			Sat	MerR
Sun	Rasi 16.02.1929 05.50 Calcutta				Navamsam		Asc/ Jup Ket
Asc/ Mer R					Ven Rah		
Sat	Ket				Sun	Mar Moo	

Venus dasa - 08 - 08 - 25

	Asc	20.38	Tiruvonam 4	1.4	Jupiter	11.53	Aswini 4
0.9	Sun	03.59	Avittm 4	1.6	Venus	20.30	Revathy 2
1.5	Moon	20.51	Bharani 3	1.5	Satturn	05.27	Moolam 2
1.1	Mars	00.18	Mirugaseersam3		Rahu	02.44	Karthika 2
1.3	Mercury R	16.49	Tiruvonam 3		Ketu	02.44	Visakam 4

Planetary Positions Causing Non - Marriage Status:

Lagna, 7th Bava, 7th Bavathipathi, Sun, if they are joined with Saturn or if they are in 2nd or 12th Bavas from that position, there is likely to be delay in marriage or no marriage if one more planetary position for delayed marriage is there. If Venus is in between Sun and Moon, will lead to inordinate delay in marriage or marriage never taking place. In this horoscope, there is Sun in Kumbha (Aquaris) and Moon in Mesha (Aries) and Venus in Meenam (Pisces). If there is no further impediment to getting married these positions will cause very delayed marriage. 2nd Lord Saturn is in 12th House. This will cause delayed marriage. 7th Lord Moon is positioned in Mars' House and Mars is in 6th Bava. Mars - Saturn have mutual 7th aspect. Mars is 11th Bavathipathi. In 11th Bava, i.e. Vrichika (Scorpio), there is the strong eunuch planet, Kethu who gains enormous strength in Vrichika (Scorpio). Given this position this individual (female) has no chance of getting married. Mars determines marriage for women. If Mars has a connection with Saturn, there will be delayed marriage and unhappiness in marriage.

Horoscope 9 - Tuesday - Pooram - Siva - Kowlava - Sukla Patsa Dwidhidai:

Ket		Mar	Ven Jup		Sun Sat	Ven	Asc/
	Rasi 16.08.1977 15.45 Delhi		Sat Sun		Ket	Navamsam	
			Moo Mer				Rah
Asc/			Rah			Jup Mer	Mar Moo

Venus Dasa - 12 - 06 - 01

	Asc	06.08	Molam 2	1.2	Jupiter	05.51	Mirugaseersam 4
1.2	Sun	29.59	Ayilyam 4	1.6	Venus	22.14	Punarpossam 1
0.8	Moon	18.23	Pooram 2	1.1	Satturn	27.22	Ayilyam 4
1.3	Mars	26.40	Mirugaseersam2		Rahu	24.24	Chithrai 1
1.0	Mercury	25.41	Pooram 4		Ketu	24.24	Revathy 3

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

Venus in 7th Bava along with Jupiter, without the aspect of an auspicious planet. This will lead to delay in marriage or even no marriage. Kaala Sarpa Yogam in 4, 10 Bavas. Lagna alone is between Rahu and Kethu. This will cause delayed marriage. Sun is in 1 minute Sandhi (Border) (29.59). Saturn Lord of 2nd and sun are joined. This will cause delayed marriage. In the above mentioned planetary positions, Jupiter will not lead to a no marriage state. Despite this individual did not get married. The only reason for this can be in his Dasa, Bukthi.

Venus Dasa: Until 12 ½ years; Sun Dasa until 18 ½; Moon Dasa until 28 ½; Mars Dasa until 35 ½; Rahu Dasa until 53 ½; Jupiter Dasa until 69 ½.

8th Bavathipathi Moon and 9th Bavathipathi Sun have exchanged Rasis. Therefore, Moon has not allowed the marriage to take place. Sun placed in the 2nd Bava to Venus is not in a position to help marriage, since he is in one Minute Sandhi losing all his powers and affecting the Bakya of this individual.

Mars Dasa: 5-12 Bavathipathi, Mars is in his own star, in the 6th Bava. This position leads to a state of no marriage.

Rahu Dasa: Rahu, aspected by Saturn, is in 10th Bava. He is in the star of Mars who is in 6th Bava. Mars is 5-12 Bavathipathi. That is why there was no chance of getting married.

Jupiter Dasa: The neutral Lagnathipathi, Jupiter is in the star of Mars. Venus, who is joined to Jupiter, is in Jupiter's star. As per the rule, the Jupiter – Venus connection in the 7th Bava did not help the marriage to take place, since there is no benefit aspects.

Horoscope 10 - Sunday - Maham - Krishna Patsa Amavasya - Pareegam - Sathus Padam:

		Rah			Sat Rah	Moo		Jup R Sun
	Rasi 26.08.1984					Navamsam		Asc/ Mer R
M		12.23 Delhi	Moo SunVen Mer R					
Jup R	Asc/ Mar Ket	Sat			Ven		Mar	Ket

Kethu Dasa - 05 - 09 - 22:

	Asc	02.57	Visakam 4	1.2	JupiterR	09.37	Moolam 3
1.2	Sun	09.41	Maham 3	1.6	Venus	29.11	Uthiram 1
0.8	Moon	02.16	Maham 1	1.1	Satturn	17.42	Swathi 4
1.3	Mars	11.06	Anusam 3		Rahu	08.23	Karthika 4
1.0	Mercury R	14.03	Pooram 1		Ketu	08.23	Anusam 2

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

Saturn in Ucha aspects 2nd Bava and retrograded 2 -5 Bavathipathi Jupiter. This will cause delay in marriage. 2nd Bavathipathi, Jupiter, and 11th Bavathipathi Mercury being retrograded points to delayed marriage. Mars joined with Kethu in Vrichika (Scorpio), aspects, from Lagna, the 7th Bava. But none of the planetary positions mentioned above lead to a non – marriage state. Therefore we need to study the Dasa, Bukthi positions. As per the Rule - Lord of 4 & 12 after Rahu's connection and if they happens to be in 4 & 12 Bava there is a likelihood that he will have Ascetic qualities. One of the main conditions is that he should remain unmarried. In this horoscope one of the condition that is 4th Lord in 12 in Rahu's Star will tempt him to be unmarried.

Kethu Dasa: Lasts until 6 years of age; Venus Dasa until 26; Sun Dasa until 32 years; Moon Dasa until 42; Mars Dasa until 49; Rahu Dasa until 69 years of age.

Venus Dasa: Although Venus is 7th Bavathipathi, he is in the star of 10th Bavathipathi Sun. He is also in 10th Bava and joined with the 10th Bavathipathi. He is not in a position to grant marriage.

Sun Dasa: Sun is in 10th Bava, and in the star of Kethu who is in Lagna. Kethu himself is in the star of 3rd- 4th Bava Lord Saturn who is in Ucha state and in the 12th Bava.

Generally Kethu does not encourage marriage; even if marriage takes place he is likely to break it. Kethu is more powerful in Vrichka (Scorpio). Therefore there is no chance of marriage.

Moon Dasa: 9th Bava Lord Moon is joined to 10th Bava Lord Sun in 10th Bava. He is also in Kethu's star. This will not allow the marriage to happen.

Mars Dasa: Mars is joined with Kethu in Lagna and aspects 7th Bava. Mars is 1 - 6 Bavathipathi. He is also in the star of his enemy, Saturn. The Lagna is neutral. 6th Bava stalls the marriage. It is unfortunate that the Dasas of planets (Venus, Sun and Moon) in the marriageable age are in 10th Bava with 10th Bavathipathi. Mars, whose Satbala is 1.5 happens to be the 6th Lord also, thus ruining all chances of marriage.

Horoscope - Sunday - Poosam - Shukla Ekadashi:

Jup Sun	Ven	Asc/ Ket	Sat		Sat	Ket		Asc/
Mer	Rasi 23.03.1975		Moo		Mer	Navamsam		Ven Mar
Mar	10.15 Delhi							
	Rah						Rah	Moo Jup Sun

Sattarn Dasa - 10 - 08 – 23

	Asc	19.35	Rohini 3	1.1	Jupiter	07.35	Uthirattathi 2
1.1	Sun	08.26	Uthirattathi 2	1.4	Venus	10.30	Aswini 4
1.5	Moon	09.02	Poosam 2	0.9	Saturn	18.31	Tiruvathirai 4
0.9	Mars	21.35	Tiruvonam 4		Rahu	10.47	Anusam 3
1.2	Mercury	16.07	Sadayam 3		Ketu	10.47	Rohini 1

Planetary Positions Causing Delay in Marriage:

Saturn is in the grip of Rahu, who is 7th Bava and is in 2nd Bava, aspects 11th Bava and 11th Bavathipathi Jupiter and Sun. Moon is in 3rd Bava and in the star of 9 -10 Bavathipathi, Saturn. However, these positions will not cause non-marriage. Therefore it is necessary to study the Dasa, Bukthi positions. Saturn Dasa until 10 ½ years; Mercury Dasa until 27 ½; Kethu Dasa until 34 ½; Venus Dasa until 54 ½; Sun Dasa until 60 ½ years of age. At the marriageable age the Dasa is Mercury- Saturn Bukthi.

Mercury Dasa: Mercury is 2nd Bavathipathi in 10th Bava. He is also in Vargothamam in Rahu's star. As for Saturn he is 9 -10th Bavathipathi and in exchange in Rahu's star in 2nd Bava. That is a reason for the marriage not taking place.

Kethu Dasa: Kethu in Lagna. Kethu is in the star of 3rd Bavathipathi, Moon. Moon is in the star of Saturn. Kethu does not encourage marriage. Their marriage is unlikely to take place in Kethu Dasa. Moon has no connection with 2nd, 7th and 11th Bavas.

Venus Dasa: Venus is neutral as Lagnathipathi + 6th Bavathipathi and in 12th Bava. Because he is in Kethu's star he blocks the happening of the marriage. In Navamsa he is in the Rasi of his enemy Moon. This too is a reason for the marriage not taking place.

Sun Dasa: Sun is in 11th Bava and in the star of 10th Bavathipathi Saturn. Also he is aspected by 10th Bavathipathi Saturn. In 11th Bava he is joined with 11th Bavathipathi. The desire for marrying may occur in the 55th year but that will come to nothing, both because of the age and the aspect of Saturn.

Horoscope - Male - Thursday - Visakam - Sobanam - Kimsthuknam - Sukla Patsa Pradamai:

		Ket	Sat R		Mar	Asc/	Sat R	Sun Ket
Jup	Rasi 14.11.1974				Jup	Navamsam		Moo Ven
Asc/	11.30 Chennai							
	Moo Rah Ven	Mer Sun Mar			Mer Rah			

Jupiter Dasa - 03 - 01 - 21:

	Asc	12.50	Tiruvonam 1	1.2	Jupiter	14.47	Sadayam 3
1.2	Sun	28.05	Visakam 3	0.9	Venus	00.01	Visakam 4
1.0	Moon	00.43	Visakam 4	0.9	Sattarn R	25.27	Punarpoosam 2
1.1	Mars	18.07	Swathi 4		Rahu	17.48	Kettai 1
1.1	Mercury	09.42	Swathi 1		Ketu	17.48	Rohini 3

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

2nd Lord Saturn is retrograded in the 6th Bava. 7th Lord Moon is in Neechabangam. He is also with Venus and Rahu. Venus is in Rasi Sandhi (Border) (00.01) in 11th Bava. These positions, however, will not lead

to a no marriage state. Therefore let us study the Dasa, Bukthi. During marriageable age, 22-39, it is Mercury Dasa. Mercury is 6th Bavathipathi and in 10th Bava. Because of this he is not in a position to aid the marriage.

Kethu Dasa: Kethu is in 7th Bavathipathi Moon's star in 5th Bava. 5th Bavathipathi Venus and 7th Bavathipathi Moon are aspect Kethu. This promotes falling in love. But Kethu will not allow the relationship to reach the state of marriage, as Kethu does not generally encourage marriage.

Venus Dasa: Venus is in Rasi Sandhi (Border). 10th Bavathipathi is in 11th Bava. Further he is in exchange with 11th Bavathipathi Mars. He is joined with 7th Lord Moon and Rahu. Rahu is in 6 - 9 Bavathipathi Mercury's star. Venus and Moon are in 3 -12 Bavathipathi Jupiter's star. Association of Rahu and Venus is in 11th Bava. The link to 3, 12, 11 Bavas causes greater desire for sexual relations. In 11th Bava, 7th Bavathipathi is in Neechabhanga and in Navamsa Moon is in his own Rasi. Given these planetary positions, no woman is likely to want to marry this individual.

Horoscope - Male - Wednesday - Mrigashirsham:

Mer Ket	Asc/ Sun	Moo Ven	Jup		Mer	Sat Rah		
	Rasi 10.05.1978 05.45		Mar			Navamsam		Ven
	Ferospur Chattisgarh		Sat		Jup			
			Rah		Mar	Asc/ Sun	Ket	Moo

Mars dasa - 04 - 10 - 24:

	Asc	25.42	Bharani 4	1.3	Jupiter	11.16	Tiruvathirai 2
1.2	Sun	25.33	Bharani 4	1.3	Venus	21.59	Rohini 4
1.1	Moon	27.20	Mirugaseersam2	0.9	SaturnR	00.24	Maham 1
1.4	Mars	18.38	Ayilyam 1		Rah	10.17	Hastham 1
1.1	Mercury	29.21	Revathy 4		Ket	10.17	Uthirattathi 3

Planetary Positions causing Delay in Marriage:

Saturn is in 5th Bava and aspecting 7, 11 and 2 Bavas from Simha (Leo). Further, he also aspects 2, 7 Bavathipathi, Venus and also Moon. Although Saturn does not aspect Sun, as he is placed in Sun's Rasi, he has a connection with Sun. This alone is enough to take the individual to a state of no marriage. Although Venus and Moon are in the same Rasi, next to Sun, if you calculate the degree, Venus is placed between Sun and Moon. This too is a reason for the marriage not taking place. The planets are not in the grip of Rahu and Kethu, thereby causing Kaala Sarpa Yogam. According to the calculation of Dasa, Bukthi, the Dasa at the time of marriageable age is Jupiter Dasa: between 23 and 39 years of age. 9-12 Bavathipathi Jupiter is in exchange with 3-6 Bavathipathi Mercury. Jupiter is in the star of Rahu who is in 6th Bava. Thus no planet is helpful for causing the marriage to take place.

Saturn Dasa: from 39- 58 years of age. Saturn is in the star of Kethu who is in Saturn's star in 12th Bava. There is star exchange. Kethu will definitely block the desire for marriage.

Mercury Dasa: 58 -75 years of age. Mercury, as 3rd and 6th Bavathipathi, in his own star, is in 12th Bava, along with Kethu. This position will block any thought of marriage in the individual. Age aids that thought.

Conclusion:

The planetary positions in a horoscope may indicate delayed marriage. Nevertheless, if the Shadbala strength of the concerned planets is more than 1.5, marriage can happen earlier than even the marriageable age fixed by the Government. However, if the Shadbala strength of the concerned planets has not reached the 1.5 level, the marriage will be delayed as per the indications in the horoscope. For unmarried persons the marriage will not happen under these conditions.

- Placement of Planets and marriage related 2, 7, 11 Bhavas and Bavathipathis in certain places.
- During the marriageable age the Dasa, Bukthi, Antharam of planets should not be linked to the 12th position of marriage related Bhavas of 2, 7, 11 that is Lagna, 6, 10th Bhava connection. However Lagna will take a neutral stand.

However Ramana Maharishi horoscope is an exception. Saturn's position in 7th house for Kanya Lagna exempts the persons from all the conditions of delayed or no marriage.

References:

1. Mridula & Prakash Trivedi - Predicting Marriage
2. Umang Taneja - Astrology & Relationship